

Performance Improvement through Strengthening Spiritual Capital with Trauma Healing Workshops

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this research is to find a method of strengthening spiritual capital within Social Service employees in border districts, in order to improve their performance. It was found that inner healing due to bitter experiences in the past can be a way of building spiritual capital. As an employee of the Social Service who provides a lot of assistance to victims of violence, competence in dealing with trauma healing is an important thing that can help carry out their duties. In fact, this trauma healing workshop does not only restore the victims who are assisted, but also builds the character of the employees themselves. In this case, the trauma healing workshop is a means of increasing the potential of spiritual capital because it has a positive impact on strengthening performance. The strengthening of this performance is evident from the effectiveness of the assistance both in terms of the timing of the assistance and the results of the assistance to the victims. This research method is a qualitative method with an ethnographic approach. Data obtained from the results of observations, interviews, and literature studies. The time spent on this research was about a year, and interviews were not only conducted with employees but also leaders and the victims of violence they assisted. Thus, this trauma healing workshop can be said as a means of strengthening spiritual capital because it has a positive impact on improving performance. In general, spiritual capital is associated with spiritual values that are instilled and have a positive impact on the organization. However, in this paper it is found that trauma healing workshops can also be a means of building character for employees which ultimately becomes a spiritual capital that strengthens employee performance.

KEYWORDS: Employee performance, Spiritual capital, Trauma healing.

INTRODUCTION

Violence against children and women often occurs everywhere. (Aryani, 2016; Suryamizon, 2017) Therefore, Social Service employees or those who work for the protection of women and children, have a noble duty to provide assistance to victims of this violence. The purpose of this research is none other than to find a method that can improve the performance of victim assistants, in the sense of being able to provide effective assistance to victims of violence. The recovery of victims of violence from all traumas is important, because past traumas can affect the attitudes, ways of thinking, and how to act in the future.

The Ministry of Women and Children's Protection stated that as of January 1, 2022 the number of cases of violence against women and children verified and being verified (in the current month) totaled 20,310 cases. Of course this is not a small amount. Therefore, good performance is needed to be able to provide effective assistance to victims of this violence.

This good performance is increasingly needed by those working in border areas. As befits existing border areas, this frontier area of the motherland is often colored by trafficking, drugs, smuggling, which often ends up in violence which results in many victims (Indahningrum et al., 2020; Laurensius Arliman S, 2016; Niko & Niko, 2017). Therefore, the role of assistants in assisting victims to experience recovery, especially psychologically, is urgent. Thus, the performance of the employees of the Office of Social Affairs or Protection of Women and Children will get better along with the more effective the assistance is carried out, both in terms of shorter time and better recovery results.

One of the assistance that needs to be provided to victims of violence in order to experience recovery is spiritual assistance, in this case trauma healing. Trauma healing is a therapy to recover someone who has been traumatized psychologically (Delić et al., 2014; Swart, 2013). Trauma healing has also been carried out in many places in Indonesia to recover victims of natural disasters who have been traumatized by the disaster. (Mulyasih & Putri, 2019; Rahman, 2018). By undergoing trauma healing, it is hoped that they will be able to live their lives normally without the shadow of fear, sadness, or other negative sentiments.

In reality, chaperones also experience spiritual strengthening when undergoing trauma healing assistance because to be able to heal others, of course you need to heal yourself first. Therefore, this paper will discuss how trauma healing can be a means of

strengthening the spiritual capital of an organization, because it can improve the performance of the organization through building the character of its members. Generally, research on trauma healing is associated with the mental recovery of people who have experienced trauma (Delić et al., 2014; Mulyasih & Putri, 2019; Rahman, 2018; Swart, 2013). However, through this research it was found that trauma healing can also be a means of increasing employee performance due to an increase in spiritual capital after the trauma healing workshop.

Organizational strengthening needs to start from strengthening its personnel first. Only then can a strong organization make a greater contribution to society in general. Weak human resources will also result in a weak organization (Moghadam & Makvandi, 2019). Especially non-profit organizations engaged in assistance for victims of violence. Strengthening an organization is not only based on financial or material matters, but especially on the spiritual appreciation of its members, because one of the works it produces is spiritual assistance. Therefore, optimizing all existing capital in an organization is an effort to make the organization more empowered.

Spiritual capital is capital that people rarely talk about. In fact, it can be said that almost every organization has spiritual capital if excavation is carried out on this capital. This happens because everyone who is a member of an organization has individual and collective capacities in strengthening the growth of spiritual values, both within himself and his organization (Palmer & Wong, 2013). This spiritual capital will play an increasingly important role in social organizations, because it requires a spirit of altruism from its members, which will grow if they have a deep appreciation of spiritual values. In many organizations and companies it is found that spiritual capital has a direct positive impact on employee motivation and performance (Hafizhah, 2019; Luthfi, 2017; Shofwa, 2013).

In the world of management and business, spiritual capital also has a big influence because it can bring benefits to the company (Cidadania, 2018; Luthfi, 2017; Pandey, 2016). More than that, even the existence of spiritual capital can also provide positive fruits for the economy (Grochmal, 2016; Yusuf, 2011). Not only in the world of management, business, or the economy, this spiritual capital is also important in an organization or social group. A study of a group of African American adults shows how their spiritual capital and religious life can be expanded into social capital (Holt et al., 2012). Meanwhile for an organization, spiritual capital can have a major impact on leadership style in the organization and can even become a handler to enforce ethics by all elements of the organization (Siddiqi et al., 2017). The link between spiritual capital and employee performance is also very close. Often a person's spiritual appreciation becomes the main source of motivation for employees, which in turn has a positive impact on their performance (Hafizhah, 2019; Pandey, 2016; Shofwa, 2013; K. Smith, 2016). Thus, the role of spiritual capital in the social life of society cannot be denied.

Especially in the midst of rampant victims of violence or disasters, this spiritual capital becomes even more important. It is said to be important because spiritual capital can help empower people working in the field to assist victims who are traumatized by violence or natural disasters. Victims need trauma healing to avoid negative psychological impacts. (Delgado, 2009; Knott & Schulz, 2012; Nihayatul Khusna & Suharso, 2019).

Recovery from this trauma is important for the victims, because if left unchecked, their social relationships will be disrupted and their recovery will take a long time. If this happens to many people, it can have a negative impact on the condition of society in the end (Delić et al., 2014). For this reason, a spiritual approach is needed that can bring these victims to a faster and better recovery at the same time (Magezi & Manda, 2016). A concrete example of this occurs in South Africa, where emotional trauma has affected the population (Swart, 2013). That is why when there was a major flood in the Pua River, traumatized children were immediately given trauma healing so that they could continue their lives normally without being overshadowed by fear because of their past experiences (Rahman, 2018). The same thing was done for children who experienced post-tsunami trauma in Sumur Banten District (Mulyasih & Putri, 2019).

The number of people who are traumatized by being victims of violence or disasters is increasing from time to time. In fact, they not only need material assistance, but more so they need help for the recovery of their wounded or traumatized minds. While the main problem is that there is not always a group of people who are ready to provide assistance for them. In this case, performance improvement is needed for those who work in this assistance, especially employees in the Social Service or in the field of women's and children's protection.

METHODS

This research method is qualitative with an ethnographic approach. This method was chosen because it requires the involvement of researchers to interpret the meanings behind social phenomena. Behind the existing social phenomena, an observation is needed to see the meaning that drives these social phenomena (Gunawan, 2013). Through qualitative research, descriptive data is produced in the form of written or spoken words from people, as well as observed behavior. The data collection technique is through field observations and in-depth interviews. In addition, literature and documentation studies were also carried out. Research is carried out from an inductive point of view to finally get contributive findings to the world of science.

Research was conducted in Bengkulu for approximately 1 year on assistants to victims of violence who were involved under the coordination of the Bengkulu Social Service. In addition, in-depth observations and interviews were carried out with Social Service employees and several victims of violence. Data and information were also obtained through Focus Group Discussions with those involved in assisting victims of violence under the coordination of the Social Service.

To reduce bias, data validation was carried out through the triangulation method. The results of observations, in-depth interviews, and literature studies were checked to see if they mutually confirm one another. This was later confirmed by the results of the Focus Group Discussion. Interpretation is carried out after codifying all valid data and information obtained, so that the meaning behind social phenomena is found based on the observations and involvement of researchers.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The increasing number of victims of violence or victims of natural disasters needs to be accompanied by an increase in the performance of employees who are tasked with providing assistance to victims. One contribution that management science can make to this is finding ways to improve employee performance so that the increasing number of victims can receive good service.

It is known that victims who experience trauma need to receive trauma healing in order to recover from all their trauma. Therefore, employees who serve as victims' assistants need to have the competence to be able to carry out trauma healing. To obtain these competencies, employees need to undergo a trauma healing workshop process.

Through this research it was found that trauma healing workshops not only improve employee competence, but more than that, can also heal the emotional wounds of the past, as well as provide new motivation for their service work in assisting victims. Many new assistants realize that they themselves actually have emotional wounds from past experiences. How could they possibly provide reparation for others if they had not recovered themselves? That is why through trauma healing workshops, employees experience inner healing, which in turn can make their work in assisting victims more effective. Apart from the fact that they have recovered, they themselves have also directly experienced the healing process that they received during the workshop. Thus, they can share this personal experience to heal others.

This valuable personal healing experience provides stronger motivation for employees to provide better and more efficient assistance to victims. The values of sharing, of ardent altruism, grow wildly in the hearts of employees. These values become spiritual capital for employees, because they strengthen their motivation and improve their performance.

Picture 1 Process The emergence of the need for competence to improve performance

A new finding in this research is that spiritual capital can be obtained through healing mental wounds. In general, spiritual capital is obtained from instilling good values in organizations, companies, traditions, families, religions, or educational institutions (Grace, 2010; Moghadam & Makvandi, 2019; C. Smith, 2015; Yunitisiah, 2014; Yusuf, 2011). However, it is now being discovered that healing emotional wounds can also generate spiritual capital for organizations.

This is because after experiencing inner healing for past painful events, employees have a strong spirit of altruism and a desire to share what they have experienced directly with others who also need inner healing.

Picture 2. Spiritual appreciation that becomes spiritual capital

The spiritual appreciation of employees in the form of a sense of altruism and a desire to share is called Spiritual Capital because it has a positive impact on the organization. As long as spiritual appreciation or internalized spiritual values do not have a positive impact, it cannot be said to be social capital (Capaldi, 2012; Mas-Machuca & Marimon, 2019). These positive impacts are as follows:

1. Employees are increasingly motivated to provide assistance to victims of violence because they themselves experience relief after undergoing trauma healing. This creates a desire to share the same thing that they have experienced, namely relief because the mind is healed through trauma healing.

2. Employee performance has also increased because assistance to victims of violence has become more optimal in terms of:
- The time needed for recovery is faster. Although everyone certainly needs a different time, it depends on how deeply he is hurt and how well the victim cooperates to want to be healed. However, in general the recovery process is faster.
 - The result is better in the sense that the victim really experiences relief and sincerity. He can live his life well without being overshadowed by the negative experiences he experienced before.
- Thus, the role of spiritual capital in this organization is none other than to strengthen employee motivation and improve employee performance.

Picture 3. The role of spiritual capital in the organization

Another finding from this research is that trauma healing workshops can be an appropriate method for strengthening the spiritual capital of an organization. This happened because after carrying out the trauma healing workshop, each employee experienced strengthening personal development or character building. This character building occurs through deep spiritual appreciation, which builds a sense of wanting to share and a spirit of altruism.

CONCLUSION

There are several conclusions from this study. First, the inner healing experienced after trauma healing can give birth to spiritual capital. This happens because these inner healing experiences kindle a deep sense of sharing and altruism, which serve to strengthen the organization. This is somewhat different from the results of other studies which generally find that spiritual capital occurs due to the inculcation of values which then become one's spiritual appreciation.

The second conclusion, spiritual capital can strengthen the organization because it can strengthen motivation and improve employee performance. This is also found in many places (Cidadania, 2018; Luthfi, 2017; Moghadam & Makvandi, 2019; Pandey, 2016). Thus, this research further confirms that spiritual capital has a big role for organizations or companies, especially for employee motivation and performance.

The third conclusion is that a trauma healing workshop can be an appropriate method for strengthening spiritual capital for an organization engaged in providing assistance to victims of violence. First, trauma healing workshops can increase employee competency in providing efficient assistance so that victims can recover from their trauma. Second, employees themselves experience recovery resulting in a burning sense of sharing and strong altruism.

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